

CLASSIFICATION OF BIOMAGNETIC PAIRS IN MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) is an integrative and non-invasive therapeutic system developed from the first Biomagnetic Pair (BMP) by the Mexican scientist Isaac Goiz Durán. MB restores the cellular bioelectric balance facilitating the prevention of pathological states. In addition, this technique may complement conventional treatment as well as reducing the convalescence and rehabilitation time of a disease. BMP is defined as a set of polarized charges in resonance with each other enabled to identify a pathology. This is built due to the fundamental alteration of the pH of the organs that support it. From this bioenergetic duality emerges another fundamental principle called Normal Energy Level (NEL) which indicates the health or illness of the individual. The treatment of the body's bioelectromagnetic dysfunctions occurs through Static Magnetic Fields (SMF) generated by magnets for the technique. The aim of this study is to present the

BMP classification in MB describing their functions and particularities. This study is a narrative, descriptive bibliographic review of an exploratory nature, based on books and MB manuals. BMP was systematically presented in order to assist therapists in improving their clinical practice. It is important to produce academic knowledge related to MB to stimulate the culture of self-care through the prevention and promotion of health.

Keywords: Medicinal Biomagnetism; Biomagnetic Pair; Classification; Static Magnetic Fields; Magnets; Magnetic Therapy.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the consolidation of science, it has become the only accepted way for unraveling the secrets of nature, rendering preconceived ideas of popular knowledge invalid (DURÁN, 2008). However, it is important to consider that together, common sense and scientific knowledge constitute elements for solving potential problems of humanity, such as in the case of the magnetism concept. Its effects are unquestionable in human physiology but due to the lack of established theoretical-practical foundations, science still disqualifies it (DURÁN, 2008).

The physician Isaac Goiz Durán developed a new model of health and disease to obtain answers about the effects of natural elements. It is based on understanding the existence of a harmonious coexistence between human beings and microorganisms in order to restore organic harmony. With a background in physiotherapy and acupuncture, the Durán aim was to challenge orthodox academic concepts by revising pathologies through alternative perspectives, especially that of Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB). It was possible after reflecting on the use of alternative medical practices, starting in 1970, when the National Institute of Pneumology underwent restructuring (DURÁN, 2008).

In 1984, Goiz participated in the World Congress of the Hispanic-American Society of Acupuncture, and in 1988, he attended the first Biomagnetism course promoted by the Society of Alternative Medicine in Guadalajara, taught by Richard Broeringmeyer. He proposed concepts of the biomagnetic man, energy,

interference of energy flow, bioenergetic health, and the polar therapy of the hydrogen potential (pH) in health and illness. These principles were called Energy Therapy (DURÁN, 1996; DURÁN, 2003; DURÁN, 2008).

Richard Broeringmeyer observed that a magnetic field, generated by a magnet may detect qualitative and indirect changes in the pH of internal organs. This change is the polarization of charges tends to generate a dysfunctional Biomagnetic Field showing that there is a constant and balanced magnetic resonance in the body that maintains health. Its dysfunction results in disease, thus, the presence of one condition its opposite (DURÁN, 2008).

After observing and practicing the principles of energy therapy, Durán combined allopathy with elements of other integrative practices such as reflexology and acupuncture. Thus, he created a simple methodology structured on the physicalchemical concept as a therapeutic basis enabled to identify the etiopathogenesis of viral and bacterial diseases and glandular dysfunctions through changes in pH; it revealed that pathogenic organisms may stay in the organs that sustain them. He used Static Magnetic Fields (SMF) of medium intensity produced by natural magnets of 1,000 to 7,500 Gauss for various therapeutic purposes (DURÁN, 2008).

Viral and bacterial diseases are related to pathological and pathogenic manifestations that arise from the polarization of opposite and well-defined charges. It departs from natural organic entropy giving rise to the Biomagnetic Pair (BMP) which are regions in bioelectromagnetic dysfunction (DURÁN, 2008).

The first BMP was identified in 1988 by Isaac Goiz Durán called "Thymus/Rectum" which supported the human immunodeficiency virus. The scanning point, which tended towards supraphysiological high-alkalinity, was located in the middle part of the sternum bone over the Thymus gland. The impaction point tended to acidity and was also called as the resonance point. It was located in the distal part of the coccyx later identified as the Rectum. As a general rule, every BMP is initially described at its scanning point and then at its resonant point, which is the point of impaction. The BMP is sustained by a magnetic field with the same

number of elementary particles and the same energetic frequency separated and maintained by a natural dielectric supporting its stability (DURÁN, 1996; DURÁN, 2003; DURÁN, 2008).

The discovery of the Thymus/Rectum BMP contradicts the theory of Broeringmeyer which was based on the cancellation of charges through magnetic fields of medium intensity when an opposite charge is positioned in the biomagnetic pole. Thus, it tends to pull the charges when the north pole of the magnet is positioned on the south biomagnetic pole and vice-versa. For the first time, Durán cancels the charges of the BMP applying magnets with equal polarities to those of the charges present at each of the BMP poles. This phenomenon has the property to push and break the dielectric canceling the existing charges (DURÁN, 2008).

Durán began to search for new BMP. By 2008, in the fifth edition of the book "The Biomagnetic Pair", 155 regular pairs, 28 special pairs, 14 pairs supporting glandular dysfunctions, 6 pairs for complex diseases, and 8 reservoir pairs had been described (DURÁN, 2008). Durán continued to identify new BMP until 2020 with the last pair composed by the Sternum/Left Lung Lingula supporting Coronavirus, shortly before his death on March 27, 2021.

The MB can act on dysfunctions of the organic systems stimulating the immune action that enables the elimination of pathogens, glandular dysfunctions, and tissue recovery. It contributed to the clinical improvement reducing the risks of infections, hemorrhages, and others. It acts in rehabilitation, prevention, and systemic pH balance promoting health (CASTEJÓN, 2015; DAMYANOV *et al.*, 2019a; DAMYANOV *et al.*, 2019b; FRANK, 2017; JIMENO, PENA, BAENA, 2014; DURÁN, 2008).

The application of magnetic fields for the treatment of specific medical problems such as arthritis, fracture and wound healing, chronic pain, insomnia, headaches, and others has been increasing constantly in the last few decades. Therefore, the aim of MB is to provide prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of dysfunctional BMP (DURÁN, 2003; DURÁN, 2008; MARKOV, 2014).

The purpose of this study is to present the classification of BMP described by Isaac Goiz Durán highlighting their functions and peculiarities.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study is a narrative, descriptive literature review based on books and manuals on the technique of Medicinal Biomagnetism. This method allows for author interaction and thematic analysis. This material was selected due to the scarcity of publications on the subject (GIL,1991).

Narrative research is characterized by collecting and narrating stories on specific topics (PAIVA, 2008). The main characteristic of descriptive studies is to describe facts without the researcher interfering in the context (GIL, 1991). The exploratory method involves a comprehensive literature review, practical experiences that involve the problem and analyzing examples that lead the reader to understand the theme (GIL, 2008).

For scientific grounding, published articles that employed the MB technique in clinical studies, as well as studies that demonstrate the action of static magnetic fields on cells, tissues, organs, and microorganisms were used. *Scielo* and *Google Scholar* databases and the online library of the *Par Magnético* Institute were used for the research.

After reading the material it was possible to extract the data and synthesize the characteristics of the BMP reported by the developer of the technique.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three references by Isaac Goiz Durán and 16 additional sources were selected as complementary literature; two of which were used for methodological grounding and 14 to support the discussion in this article, resulting in a total of 19 cited works.

The count of the Biomagnetic Pairs that are the aim of this study was based on the Medicinal Biomagnetism manual, called the Medicinal Biomagnetism

Scanning Protocol, in its first edition of August 2021, from the *Par Magnético* Institute (IPM) (BOSSA, 2021). This material is a compilation that reviewed all the books and courses developed by Goiz and his team until December 2020. It was developed for the Postgraduate Course in Biomagnetism and Bioenergetics Applied to Health according to Table 1.

The BMP are classified for their study into: Regular Pairs, Reservoir Pairs, Psycho-emotional Pairs, Special Pairs, Dysfunctional Pairs, Pairs for Complex Diseases, Temporal or Transitory Pairs, Associated Pairs, Reciprocal Pairs, Inverted Pairs, Symmetrical Pairs, and Asymmetrical Pairs.

Table 1: BMP classification for the MB treatment

Biomagnetic Pair classification	"El Par Biomagnético" (DURÁN, 2008)	Medicinal Biomagnetism Scanning Protocol (BOSSA, 2021)
Regular	155	247
Reservoir	08	62
Psycho-emotional	-	26
Special	28	56
Dysfunctional	14	14
Complex Diseases	06	17
Temporal/Transitory	--	--
Associated	--	--
Reciprocal	--	--
TOTAL	211	422

Only the BMP classification was used here according to the description of Durán adding the BMP presented in 2008 and until 2020 with the release of the last identified pair (BOSSA, 2021). Source: The authors.

Only the BMP classification was used here according to the description of Durán adding the BMP presented in 2008 and until 2020 with the release of the last identified pair (BOSSA, 2021). Source: The authors.

The Regular Pairs group common pathologies supported by only one microbiological entity, that is, they are related to specific pathogenic microorganisms, including viruses, bacteria, fungi, parasites, or archaea. Durán

(2008) describes that a regular pair supports two microorganisms, one of which is located in the region of the north pole and the other in the south pole. While one of these microorganisms is pathogenic – triggering signs and symptoms – the other is structural providing support to the pathogenic microorganism.

The north pole favors the permanence and proliferation of bacteria and parasites while the south pole favors viruses and fungi. A study by Frank (2017) used the technique of MB in 13 patients with typhoid fever confirmed by tests. After the application of BMP related to *Salmonella typhi*, 10 of the 13 participants tested negative when they underwent the same participants to test again.

An example of a Regular Pair is the Right or Left Axilla/Contralateral Axilla BMP which may be related to the rabies virus. It is located in the upper part of the axilla, the highest point of the axillary line, and should be impacted bilaterally. The resonance is also located in the upper part of the contralateral axilla at the highest point of the axillary line (DURÁN, 2008).

Special Pairs are related to organic dysfunctions that are not caused by infections from pathogenic microorganisms or internal glandular dysfunctions but rather to specific organ alterations with pathological or symptomatic repercussions, totally special in terms of office symptomatology. In other words, they can identify tissue alterations not supported by pathogenic microorganisms (DURÁN, 2008).

Most of these pairs are titled with proper names, such as the first one that was identified as the “Goiz Pair”. Gradually, these pairs formed a special group with names of relatives, students, or patients in whom they were identified (BOSSA, 2019; DURÁN, 2008).

The BMP has some particularities: while some support alterations that host chronic diseases, such as Parkinson’s, endometriosis, and diabetes mellitus, others support signs and symptoms in the acute phase, such as diarrhea, renal colic, temporary loss of taste caused by infectious diseases. In addition, some may be used for prevention of complications and evolution of pathologies, such

as fibromyalgia and multiple sclerosis, and still others may act on various dysfunctions and intoxications.

An example of a Special Pair is the Goiz BMP in which the magnets are placed on the Parietal and contralateral Kidney. This is the only pair that is applied starting with the south pole of the magnet, impacting the indicated kidney first and then applying the north pole of another magnet on the contralateral parietal, located on the posterior lateral part of the skull, opposite to the impacted kidney. This pair may resonate with other organs of the skull, mainly with the ears, parathyroids, or parotids, but always on the contralateral side and always starting the impaction with the positive pole on the kidney. The symptoms produced by the presence of this pair may vary and could be related to the central nervous system, bronchopulmonary system, or renal system. The manifestation of this BMP may be associated with hypocalcemia, muscle weakness, motor disorders, recurrent bronchitis, and a tendency towards urinary tract infection (DURÁN, 2008; BOSSA, 2021).

Dysfunctional Pairs specifically identify abnormalities in gland function affecting hormonal production. They are also related to the modulation of organ productivity and are considered rehabilitation pairs. Thus, this category of BMP is not only related to endocrine secretion glands but also to organs and viscera such as the stomach and spleen (DURÁN, 2008; MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

These pairs are also classified because they represent a group of pairs used for the treatment of health problems due to hormonal changes. They are classified as special because of the relationship with tissue dysfunctions. Such dysfunctions may be caused by the presence of Regular Pairs near the glands and/or organs. The microorganisms that sustain regular BMP may produce toxins or endotoxins that alter the environment of the gland/organ. This results in a change in pH region affecting the physiological functioning of structures which then develop a dysfunctional special pair. According to Bossa (2021), all BMP are interrelated and the more pairs associated, the greater the likelihood of leading to new symptoms or worsening of existing ones, as we will see later in the complex disease pairs (DURÁN, 2008; MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

To illustrate Dysfunctional Pairs, the Ovary(R/L)/Ovary dysfunction BMP may be applied to both the contralateral ovary and the Ipsilateral (IPS), i.e., the same side. This ovarian dysfunction may be primary or secondary to an infectious process. The presence of this BMP may lead to symptoms such as menstrual flow irregularity, infertility, cramps, early menopause, endometriosis, cysts, polycystic ovaries (DURÁN, 2008; BOSSA, 2021).

To assist in the treatment of psycho-emotional disorders, Durán developed Psycho-emotional Pairs which are related to personality and/or the psychological sphere of the person (DURÁN, 2008; MARTÍNEZ, 2018). One of the BMP that fits into this category is the pair related to the lack of positioning where there is no coherence between thoughts, feelings, and actions. This pair was named “Character” and may be identified in people who have difficulty, for example, in saying no or people who go against their own will for the sake of others’ will. The application of this pair is in the Interciliary region and the Spinal Bulb; Durán named as “David” (DURÁN, 2008; MARTÍNEZ, 2018). These pairs are classified as psycho-emotional but they are also special pairs because of the relationship to tissue dysfunctions.

Complex Pairs define some dysfunctional pathologies that encompass other systems and tissues (DURÁN, 2008). It is not related to infectious diseases, organic dysfunctions, or psycho-emotional problems. Although they are related to multifactorial diseases such as chronic-degenerative, autoimmune, metabolic, tumor, intoxications, injuries, or sequelae of diseases, these BMP are also considered special because they may be used as a complement in the treatment of various diseases related to tissue dysfunctions (MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

These pairs are always identified in conjunction with other BMP mainly regular and dysfunctional ones. They may be present in the patient’s body even without the organic manifestation of signs and symptoms of a particular disease which represents a prophylactic therapeutic potential of the technique of Medicinal Biomagnetism.

The pair Nose (R/L)/Nose (contralateral) is an example of this type of BMP related to dysfunctions that could lead to allergic rhinitis. Its impaction may help with the cleaning of the sinuses which acts as a barrier against the entry of possible viral infections that may lead to other diseases and dysfunctions (DURÁN, 2008; BOSSA, 2021).

Reservoir pairs are pairs where pathogenic microorganisms may be indefinitely lodged in a state of latency. They identify organs or tissues that potentially support possible antigens. Their main characteristic is that they may temporarily harbor microorganisms related to regular BMP and, when impacted, restore their usual positioning (DURÁN, 2008; MARTÍNEZ, 2017). These are classified in a separate way, scanned at the beginning of the MB session immediately before the complete scanning. Most Reservoir Pairs are also included in the list of Regular Pairs throughout the complete scanning.

Regarding particularities in Reservoir BMP, the pathogen could cause few or no symptoms as a result of being in a state of latency. Durán describes that although there are places in the human body that are more likely to maintain microorganisms in a state of latency, in accordance with natural physiological characteristics and the affinity that many microorganisms have for certain pH values, all cells may be reservoirs of viruses, and parasites may be reservoirs of bacteria. In 2020, while teaching his courses, Durán explained that all long bones may be universal reservoirs which are places that could harbor viruses, fungi, bacteria, and parasites, or any type of pathogen, thus increasing the number of identified Reservoir BMP. An example of a Reservoir BMP is the pair named "Congress" by Durán, which is a reservoir of parasites anatomically located between the iliac bones (inter-iliac) and the sacrum.

Temporal Pairs, also called Transit Pairs by Martínez (2018), are formed acutely mainly due to traumas, automatically depolarized as the immunological healing process occurs. These spontaneously cease but may be impacted usually with the north pole of the magnet on the trauma and the south pole on the Ipsilateral kidney. This is the most common transient pair, known as "Trauma Pair", which acts as an antiinflammatory pair. It is used for general drainage (the area to be

drained is identified as the conflict resolution zone) and also in special impactation for the treatment of tumor, vascular, potential spaces, and flow alterations (blood, lymphatic, humoral, air, reticuloendothelial, and special). An example of this application is the pair Joint/Kidney (usually ipsilateral) along the complex scanning where the north pole can be impacted on any joint.

The Temporal Pairs may also be impacted by the Double Magnet (a magnet with both polarities on the same face of the tool) used in MB as an analgesic. The Joint/Kidney pair may also be used in this case by applying a Double Magnet on the joint and another on the kidney as indicated in the scanning. Generally, this type of pair is individual to each organism and is not included in the BMP of the MB Complete Scanning Protocol, as they are identified in the scanning to treat a specific trauma, according to the patient's semiology (DURÁN, 2008; BOSSA, 2010).

There are Associated Pairs that represent BMP. When presented in the organism and related to the same signs and symptoms, the greater the severity of the pathologies. Thus, the more chronic or multifactorial the disease, the greater and more complex the association of BMP.

In his studies and clinical practices, Durán observed that tumoral phenomena are related to the association of microorganisms that have a preference for specific sites, that is, for BMP that sustain a biological terrain contributing to their development. As microorganisms require a specific environment with appropriate pH levels and substrates, it is acceptable to theorize that they have more affinity for some regions. Thus, for Medicinal Biomagnetism, tumoral phenomena develop and evolve through the association of pairs (DURÁN, 2003).

The evolution of a tumoral phenomenon theorized by Durán (2003) may be illustrated when we consider the bioenergetic etiology of the tumoral phenomenon from the association of two BMP that support DNA viruses. When another BMP of support for parasite, fungus, or bacteria is associated, the staging evolves to an exudate. The association of other BMP increases the complexity of the physiopathogenic phenomenon, developing from there processes of

dysplasias, benign and malignant neoplasms, and finally generating metastases and necroses.

The Reciprocal Pairs are related of an organ dysfunction and are polarized with double charge in the same anatomical region. The impaction of this pair requires the application of two magnets, one with a north polarity and another with a south polarity, such as the Liver/Liver BMP (DURÁN, 2008).

The types of BMP described above are complemented by Martínez (2018) with three distinct classifications, namely Inverted, Symmetrical, and Asymmetrical Pairs. The Inverted Pairs are those that invert their charges, conditioning the polarity exchange of the magnets during their application in the organism. The Symmetrical Pairs are found in bilateral points such as Ear/Ear which may have the scanning point on the right side and the impactor on the left, or vice versa. A characteristic of these pairs is that usually the north pole of the BMP is on the right side of the body, and this tendency is greater in the inhabitants of the northern hemisphere of the planet. Thus, it is necessary to scan with the magnet testing the result obtained by bioenergetics (DURÁN, 2008).

Finally, the Asymmetric Pairs are found in anatomical structures that do not associate bilaterally, such as Thymus/Rectum. Some peculiarities need to be observed when, for example, an asymmetric pair could also assume the characteristics of an inverted pair: the case when the Rectum becomes the scanner and the Thymus becomes the impactor, thus forming a Regular, Inverted and Asymmetric Rectum/Thymus pair. In this case, the signals and symptoms formed may diverge from the Thymus/Rectum BMP. The same does not occur with Symmetric Pairs, such as the Ear/Ear BMP which is regular and inverted, but the semiology remains the same.

Medicinal Biomagnetism is based on the distortion of two specific points for each pathogenic microorganism or glandular dysfunction. It maintains distorted due to supra-physiological acidity and alkalinity beyond the limit of relative neutrality. For the treatment of these pairs, the MB session corresponds to three main stages: the first consisting the Complete Scanning (CS) which is performed

through kinesiological tests scanning the more than 200 anatomical points of the human body; the second stage occurs after the identification of the corresponding resonance point where the BMP is found and where the second magnet will be impacted; the third is consisted by the depolarization stage, where the magnets remain impacted for a time that may vary from 5-45 minutes depending on the geographic location of the person receiving the session. The objective of the treatment is to restore the organism's Normal Energy Level (NEL) thus completing the depolarization of the impacted region. After the completion of the depolarization process, the expected result is for the organism to return to a state of health (MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

The Table 1 describes a limited number of BMP but there are 422 described BMP actually (BOSSA, 2021b; DURÁN, 2008). According to Martínez, the current director of the Isaac Goiz Durán Medical Biomagnetism School, the Complete Scanning Protocol is closed and new BMP will be considered as Transitory Pairs (MARTÍNEZ, 2022).

This study is important to understand the treatment process that occur in the organism. Since the scanning and impaction on the identified points with alterations are completed, the role of the magnets begins the process of balancing dysfunctional bioelectric charges in the organism. A child may have a faster depolarization process than an adult considering that different pairs may have different depolarization times. It could be related to the pathogenicity, the time of disease evolution, and the distance from the Equator line (MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

According to the sequence of treatment followed by a MB therapist in relation to the Regular and Reservoir Pairs, it was possible to visualize a relationship between pathogens and magnetoresistance. When the professional performs the scanning in their practice and immediately impacts the BMP before taking note of the information, there is a correction of active points avoiding the repositioning of magnets and the magnetoresistance of possible identified microorganisms. On the other hand, when the therapist identifies a BMP and then takes note of it before impacting, this may favor the need to reposition the

magnets facilitating the magnetoresistance process acquired by pathogens in the BMP. This is due to the higher probability of displacement of these pathogenic agents or even the ability to invert their polarity, the longer the time between the identification of the BMP and its impactation (MARTÍNEZ, 2018). This last information is a theory that needs to be studied.

In these cases, it is recommended to allow an interval of 5 to 10 days between the impactations of the same BMP. This recommended interval is intended to offer the organism the time for bioelectromagnetic and biochemical reorganization promoting the elimination of toxins due to changes in the biological terrain. In addition, it also avoids the acquisition of magnetoresistance by microorganisms contributing to recover the NEL (MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

Dysfunctional, special, complex, and psycho-emotional pairs may be impacted, if necessary, for periods of 20-30 minutes on alternate days, one day on and two days off, making a cycle of 3-5 impacts, always conducting a complete scanning afterwards (MARTÍNEZ, 2018). In clinical practice, it is also observed that these periods may be longer in relation to the impactation time of the BMP or the total number of days of tool use. It is also observed that sometimes there is no need for interval days between applications. The continuous use of these types of pairs may enhance the effect of the Complete Scanning, modulating tissue activities and promoting health. Home use, guided by a qualified professional, promotes self-care, acting in the prevention of dysfunctions that could lead to the development and worsening of signs and symptoms of the pathologies.

4. CONCLUSION

MB is a therapeutic tool that has not been studied in high methodological rigor clinical trials. Its publications are scarce and conducted as a singular therapy for treating health problems in a simple method. This study classified the Biomagnetic Pairs as described by the technique's developer aiming to assist in future research that evaluates the method.

Understanding the particularities and precautions to be taken when depolarizing and treating each type of pair is essential for the development of

systematic and rigorously conducted research. It is crucial to conduct studies that evaluate the MB technique, correlating the Biomagnetic Pairs, their characteristics, and the symptoms described by Isaac Goiz Durán. In this way, the culture of self-care could be stimulated through prevention and promotion of health.

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in human physiology but due to the lack of established theoretical-practical

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